

SMARANDACHE REVERSE AUTO CORRELATED SEQUENCES AND SOME FIBONACCI DERIVED SMARANDACHE SEQUENCES

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Let $a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots$ be a base sequence. We define a **Smarandache Reverse Auto-correlated Sequence (SRACS)** $b_1, b_2, b_3, \dots$ as follow :

$b_1 = a_1^2, b_2 = 2a_1a_2, b_3 = a_2^2 + 2a_1a_3, \dots$ by the following transformation

$$b_n = \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \cdot a_{n-k+1}$$

and such a transformation as **Smarandache Reverse Auto Correlation Transformation (SRACT)**

We consider a few base sequences.

(1) $1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

i.e. ${}^1C_1, {}^2C_1, {}^3C_1, {}^4C_1, {}^5C_1, \dots$

The SRACS comes out to be

$1, 4, 10, 20, 35, \dots$ which can be rewritten as

i.e. ${}^3C_3, {}^4C_3, {}^5C_3, {}^6C_3, {}^7C_3, \dots$ we can call it SRACS(1)

Taking this as the base sequence we get SRACS(2) as

$1, 8, 36, 120, 330, \dots$ which can be rewritten as

i.e. ${}^7C_7, {}^8C_7, {}^9C_7, {}^{10}C_7, {}^{11}C_7, \dots$. Taking this as the base sequence we get SRACS(3) as

$1, 16, 136, 816, 3876, \dots$

i.e. ${}^{15}C_{15}, {}^{16}C_{15}, {}^{17}C_{15}, {}^{18}C_{15}, {}^{19}C_{15}, \dots,$

This suggests the possibility of the following :

conjecture-I

The sequence obtained by 'n' times Smarandache Reverse Auto Correlation Transformation (SRACT) of the set of natural numbers is given by the following:

SRACS(n)

${}^{h-1}C_{h-1}, {}^hC_{h-1}, {}^{h+1}C_{h-1}, {}^{h+2}C_{h-1}, {}^{h+3}C_{h-1}, \dots$ where $h = 2^{n+1}$.

(2) **Triangular number as the base sequence:**

1, 3, 6, 10, 15, ...

i.e. ${}^2C_2, {}^3C_2, {}^4C_2, {}^5C_2, {}^6C_2, \dots$

The SRACS comes out to be

1, 6, 21, 56, 126, ... which can be rewritten as

i.e. ${}^5C_5, {}^6C_5, {}^7C_5, {}^8C_5, {}^9C_5, \dots$ we can call it SRACS(1)

Taking this as the base sequence we get SRACS(2) as

1, 12, 78, 364, 1365, ...

i.e. ${}^{11}C_{11}, {}^{12}C_{11}, {}^{13}C_{11}, {}^{14}C_{11}, {}^{15}C_{11}, \dots$, Taking this as the base sequence we get SRACS(3) as

1, 24, 300, 2600, 17550, ...

i.e. ${}^{23}C_{23}, {}^{24}C_{23}, {}^{25}C_{23}, {}^{26}C_{23}, {}^{27}C_{23}, \dots$,

This suggests the possibility of the following

conjecture-II

The sequence obtained by 'n' times Smarandache Reverse Auto Correlation transformation (SRACT) of the set of Triangular numbers is given by

SRACS(n)

${}^{h-1}C_{h-1}, {}^hC_{h-1}, {}^{h+1}C_{h-1}, {}^{h+2}C_{h-1}, {}^{h+3}C_{h-1}, \dots$ where $h = 3.2^n$.

This can be generalised to conjecture the following:

Conjecture-III :

Given the base sequence as ${}^nC_n, {}^{n+1}C_n, {}^{n+2}C_n, {}^{n+3}C_n, {}^{n+4}C_n, \dots$

The SRACS(n) is given by

${}^{h-1}C_{h-1}, {}^hC_{h-1}, {}^{h+1}C_{h-1}, {}^{h+2}C_{h-1}, {}^{h+3}C_{h-1}, \dots$ where $h = (n+1).2^n$.